

DIAGNOSIS OF SPEECH COMPETENCE IN A DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT THROUGH TESTING TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. *The paper addresses the challenges of digital assessment regarding professional speech skills among students majoring in civil engineering: building and structural construction during English for Specific Purposes (ESP) classes. To eliminate the subjectivity and limitations inherent in conventional oral testing, an automated evaluation software was developed on the MS Excel platform and subjected to experimental testing. The software enables a human-factor-free, objective pedagogical diagnosis, measuring both the students' proficiency in field-specific texts, blueprints, and professional case-studies, and their response latency (time tracking). The empirical findings demonstrate that this digital approach provides accurate group performance metrics, identifies invalid or overly complex items within the test bank for further refinement, allows for targeted self-study assignments based on individual learning gaps, and facilitates the optimization of curriculum mapping.*

Keywords: *digital environment, speech competence, pedagogical diagnostics, test technologies, evaluation criteria, MS Excel, civil engineering, independent study, time limit.*

INTRODUCTION. Today, the digitalization of education is not limited to the mere use of computer technologies; it constitutes a comprehensive system for monitoring and assessing students' actual level of knowledge in real time. In this context, the discipline "English for Specific Purposes" (ESP) acquires particular importance for students majoring in civil engineering. This is driven by the widespread adoption of international standards, advanced foreign technologies, and the experience of cooperating with foreign partners on modern construction sites. Accordingly, the effective formation of future engineers' professional speech competence in English and, most importantly, its objective assessment constitute one of the pressing problems of the modern higher-education system.

The content of English classes for students of engineering specialties should not be limited to the study of general grammar or the development of everyday conversational skills. Future specialists need to be able to read technical texts in the field of construction, to interpret design documentation, and to describe the elements of drawings in a foreign language. Diagnosing such complex professional skills by means of traditional forms of assessment (such as a standard oral survey or a paper-based written questionnaire) proves difficult. In this regard, the application of digital test technologies that are adapted to practice-oriented tasks and possess a high degree of pedagogical-measurement accuracy serves today as a reliable and valid instrument.

In our republic, too, a national system for assessing knowledge and skills is being actively developed, and the issues of testology are receiving attention at the state level. However, in the practice of higher education, the digital diagnosis of future engineers' professional speech abilities, as well as the determination of the dynamics of learning-material mastery on the basis of time indicators, still remains insufficiently studied. Within the framework of our dissertation research, a methodology of collaborative (joint) learning was developed, and electronic testing tools were

applied as a diagnostic instrument for verifying changes in the educational process. This made it possible to accurately measure the level of command of special terminology and to record the speed at which students complete practical tasks.

LITERATURE REVIEW. The problems of the digital diagnosis of speech competences on the basis of time norms, as well as the issues of testology, have been studied extensively in both domestic and world pedagogical science. At the international level, the theoretical foundations of language-competence testing and the modeling of test items were laid down in the fundamental works of such major Western scholars as L. Bachman and A. Palmer [1]. In their research they developed criteria for ensuring the validity and reliability of language tests. In turn, the problems of language learning in a digital environment and the assessment of computer-assisted language testing (CALT) were systematized by C. Chapelle [2].

Among the scholars of the CIS countries, I. A. Zimnyaya and A. A. Leontiev [3], having analyzed the types of speech activity from a psycholinguistic standpoint, revealed the internal mechanisms of the formation of speech competence. In the field of the methodology of test systems and pedagogical measurements — in particular, the mathematical-statistical analysis of the difficulty level of test items on the basis of modern test theory (IRT — Item Response Theory) — the studies of V. S. Avanesov and M. B. Chelyshkova [5] are foundational.

While the issues of introducing targeted pedagogical technologies into the educational process in our republic were investigated by O. T. Parpiev, A. R. Khodjabaev, and G. M. Anorkulova, the problems of developing students' foreign-language communicative abilities were reflected in the works of T. S. Bazarova and N. P. Khinzeeva [6, 7]. In turn, the mechanisms for creating problem situations in instruction were theoretically substantiated by M. Jabbarov and J. Nodirov.

Nevertheless, despite the existence of numerous global studies in the field of linguodidactic testing and the theory of pedagogical measurements, the methodological aspect of diagnosing the professional speech competence of construction-profile students in English classes — with the integration of precise time parameters and the toolkit of the MS Excel electronic database — has not yet been examined as an independent object of comprehensive research.

METHODOLOGY. In the process of diagnosing and digitally assessing the professional speech competence of students majoring in construction (industrial and civil construction) in English classes, a combination of the systems approach and experimental-pedagogical methods was used. In order to monitor and measure the effectiveness of the collaborative-learning methodology developed within the research, special automated software for assessment and analysis (a computer program) was created in the Microsoft Excel spreadsheet environment and put into practice [8, 9].

This methodological approach allows the teacher, upon the completion of a class, to record the overall performance percentage of an academic group, to single out the topics or specific test items in which students made the greatest number of errors, and to promptly adjust the calendar-and-thematic plans of subsequent classes as well as the assignments for students' independent work.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. In the process of developing a methodology for the development of foreign-language speech competence on the basis of a collaborative approach, the test form of assessment was applied as the principal diagnostic instrument for verifying the effectiveness of the ongoing changes in the educational process. The use of modern test items made it possible to carry out a differentiated assessment of students' speech competence, to

identify the dynamics of its mastery, and to provide a scientific justification for the practical results of the methodology being introduced. In addition, the test-based monitoring of the competences formed within the collaborative approach helped to reveal in students such skills as independent thinking, communicativeness, and the ability to seek solutions in problem situations by means of language.

Students majoring in civil engineering study English primarily for professional communication, for working with technical documentation, and for communicating with foreign partners. To achieve these aims, test-based assessment makes it possible to evaluate the following skills and abilities of students with a high degree of accuracy [9, 10, 11]:

- understanding technical texts (Reading for Engineering Purposes);
- the correct use of terminological units in a professional context;
- the ability to describe the elements of building structures in English;
- the interpretation of technical instructions in oral and written form;
- commenting on and analyzing design materials in English, and so on.

Since the test assessment is adapted directly to professional-communicative tasks, a high objectivity is ensured in reflecting the real learning outcomes of students on specific topics.

Within our dissertation research, scientific-research work was carried out on the introduction of the testing method on the basis of such practice-oriented tasks and on identifying its new didactic aspects.

In developing English tests adapted to the construction field, the basic measurement criteria adopted were not general linguistic knowledge but professionally oriented competences (in accordance with the qualification requirements of the field of education). In the process of constructing test items, particular attention was paid to the following aspects:

- Mastery of professional terminology. For example, differentiating the meanings and semantic content of such construction terms as “beam,” “reinforced concrete,” “foundation,” “load-bearing wall,” “soil pressure,” and “span length.”
- Designing questions on the reading of technical articles and manuals. On the basis of a specialized text describing construction processes, test questions are formed to identify the key idea and to capture technical parameters and normative safety requirements.
- Compiling test items on the basis of graphic materials and drawings. The student is presented with a design drawing for which questions are developed, aimed at verifying knowledge of the English-language names, functions, and structural features of the elements shown.
- Professionally oriented situational test items (case-tests). Questions are formed on the basis of modeling real production situations, such as a “Construction site meeting,” a “Technical report presentation,” and “Equipment installation instructions.”

Such test items make it possible to determine, with a high degree of accuracy, the student’s level of readiness to apply English effectively under the conditions of real engineering and production activity.

Within this process, on the basis of integrating the foreign language with the major disciplines (Introduction to the Construction Specialty), test items were developed on 2–3 key topics. Each topic was structured into 3 content blocks, in each of which 3 test questions were formed. The test-item bank created in this way served as the basis for an objective assessment of students’ knowledge by means of specialized software developed in the MS Excel environment.

According to the program's operating algorithm, before testing begins the student enters personal data: surname, first name, academic-group number, and the name of the academic discipline. A built-in electronic database ensures the automatic saving of individual test results. After the students of a group complete the tasks of the first block, the program performs an automated statistical analysis of the data obtained and generates a summary result in the form of a graphic chart [11] (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Graphic representation of the indicators of students' overall and average performance by topic, based on the developed computer software.

On the basis of an analysis of the academic group's answers to the test items, it becomes possible to provide a scientific justification of the level of mastery of the first and second thematic modules. According to the results reflected in the chart, the mastery indicators of the first blocks of the first and second topics amounted to 60–75%, whereas the second and third blocks were mastered in the range of 50–80%. Proceeding from these data, the lecturer focuses attention precisely on those content components of the topics that caused the greatest difficulties, which makes it expedient to integrate them into the structure of the assignments for students' independent work. In the context of teaching adjacent sequential disciplines, it appears expedient to conduct an initial knowledge diagnosis (a pre-test) in the first lecture of the semester. This makes it possible to determine students' baseline level of preparation and, on the basis of the data obtained, to revise the distribution of academic hours allocated to the topics in the calendar-and-thematic plan, with its subsequent re-approval. Minimizing the duplication of material already mastered by students prevents a decline in learning motivation (the boredom effect) and ensures the rational use of academic time.

In the course of the time-based monitoring of the process of students' knowledge mastery through testing, examinations on the topics covered are carried out on the basis of the above-mentioned conditions. The results obtained make it possible to differentiate the level of knowledge and cognitive preparation of students for each content block of a topic. After the degree of understanding of the learning material has been recorded, the developed software is used to determine the time indicators (timing) spent on completing the test items. The values obtained from the software complex are presented in the form of a specialized chart (Fig. 2). On the basis of an integral analysis of these indicators (the ratio of answer correctness to the time spent), the index of descriptive difficulty of the developed test items is determined.

Fig. 2. Graphic representation of the average time indicators spent on completing each test item by topic, based on the computer software.

Within the developed methodology, the teacher forms a test-item bank, allocating 4 questions to each academic topic (the number of questions may vary). The software complex developed in the MS Excel environment is adapted to process tests consisting of 20 questions, with the possibility of scaling the final grade on a 15- or 20-point system. When assessment is conducted in academic groups with an average size of 20–25 students, the prepared test materials are distributed among the learners.

Students record their answers within the established time regulation on special answer sheets. Once the time has elapsed, the teacher collects the examination materials and performs a binary digitization of the data: a correct answer is coded as “1,” an incorrect one as “0.” These indicators are entered into the corresponding rows of the spreadsheet, linked to the personal data (surname and first name) of each student. The program’s built-in algorithms automatically perform a comprehensive statistical analysis of the entered results.

Fig. 3. Graphic representation of the individual level of mastery of the learning material by topic (Student A as an example).

An analysis of this chart makes it possible to state that the student demonstrated a low level of mastery in the 2nd and 4th thematic modules, whereas high indicators were recorded for the 1st and 3rd topics. The overall level of mastery of the material across all topics amounted to 50%. To improve academic performance in this discipline, the student needs to undertake additional

independent study and to intensify the work with specialized literature on the 2nd and 4th modules, which will ultimately contribute to the growth of the individual educational result.

Such monitoring makes it possible to determine, in a differentiated manner, each learner's level of mastery of the discipline and to issue, in good time, targeted assignments on the specific topics that require knowledge correction.

Fig. 4. The overall index of students' mastery of the material by topic.

Analyzing this chart, we see that the learners mastered topics 1, 2, and 4 at a low level, and topics 3 and 5 at a satisfactory level. The overall level of mastery of the material by topic is 49%. To raise the overall level of the learners' mastery of the material in this group, topics 1, 2, and 4 should be repeated and advanced pedagogical technologies should be used.

Figure 5 shows, in the form of a chart, the learners' overall level of command of each test question.

Fig. 5. The overall level of the learners' mastery of the material for each test question.

Analyzing this diagram, we see that questions 2, 7, and 15 of the test are difficult, while questions 8, 10, and 12 are very easy. We will examine the difficult and the very easy structured questions of the test.

Despite the existence of broad opportunities for monitoring and assessing students' theoretical and practical knowledge, skills, and qualifications, this issue is not regarded as a pressing pedagogical problem. On the whole, the problems of determining the level of students' professional preparation have not been fully resolved.

CONCLUSION. At present, it is difficult to objectively assess the professional oral-speech skills of construction students who study in English by means of traditional oral surveys and to accurately identify the gaps in their knowledge. The automated electronic testing program developed within this research on the Microsoft Excel platform made it possible to ensure objective and accurate pedagogical control without human participation. The experimental tests conducted using the program demonstrated clearly, by means of graphs and charts, the extent to which students mastered the texts, drawings, and professional situational tasks pertaining to the field, and how much time they spent on each question. As a result of the analysis, it was established that the group's overall level of material mastery amounted to 49 percent, and that some questions in the test bank turned out to be too difficult (questions 2, 7, 15) or too easy, which created an opportunity to reformulate them.

On the basis of the results obtained, it is recommended that subject teachers, during the lesson, rework the topics that the learners have mastered insufficiently, using advanced pedagogical technologies, and that, depending on the individual results of each student, they assign targeted independent tasks on the topics he or she has not mastered. Likewise, for adjacent and sequential subjects, it is necessary to determine the learners' level of knowledge at the beginning of the semester by means of these electronic tests and to redistribute the hours in the calendar-and-thematic plan on this basis. This measure will make it possible to avoid the learners' repetition of already-studied topics in the lesson, to eliminate their sense of boredom, and to fully rule out the wasting of time in the learning process.

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